

THE INCIDENCE OF RHINOSINUSITIS AMONG ENT DISEASES IN SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN

1. Nurov U.I.,
2. Khazratov O.R.,
3. Rashidov D.R

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7638821>

Relevance. According to American researchers, 4.6% of all visits to a general practitioner are for cases of rhinosinusitis. Acute bacterial rhinosinusitis is the 5th most common antibiotic prescription in children [1,3]. Each child suffers acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI) up to 6-8 times a year, which are often complicated by rhinosinusitis [4]. Every year, the number of patients with inflammation of the paranasal sinuses increases by 1.5–2%. Acute rhinosinusitis accounts for 9 to 20% of all childhood ENT diseases. The prevalence of diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses in children is 28–30% of all diseases of the upper respiratory tract, and about 50% of children, becoming adults, continue to suffer from these diseases [2,5].

Thus, the most important factors in the development of rhinosinusitis are inflammation and swelling of the mucous membrane of the nasal cavity and sinuses, impaired aeration and drainage, viral and bacterial infection. The nature of the course of ARS in children depends on the etiology of the disease, as well as on the age of the patient.

Research materials and methods. To assess the prevalence of acute sinusitis in the structure of ENT pathology in children at the Bukhara hospital stage of medical care. To assess the prevalence of AS in the structure of ENT pathology in children, an analysis was made of outpatient cards and case histories of children who applied to the emergency department and were hospitalized in the ENT department. The diagnosis was made based on anamnestic data, clinical-instrumental and laboratory analysis results.

Research results. Children of primary school age (7-12 years old) - 31.25%, senior school children age (12-18 years) - 26.79%. The study included patients from 7 to 18 years of age with a clinically and radiologically confirmed diagnosis of mild to moderate AS, with no signs of a chronic process in the mucous membrane of the PNS and a disease duration of not more than 4 weeks, who did not receive treatment with systemic antibacterial and antiviral drugs. Patients younger than 1 year and older than 18 years, with a symptom duration of more than 4 weeks, with signs of a chronic process in the mucous membrane of the PNS, treated with systemic antibacterial and antiviral drugs, were not included in the study.

According to our data, among children who received assistance at the level of the admission department of a hospital, the number of patients with AS was 5.7%: fluctuations ranged from 2.5% to 8.2% depending on the season. The ratio of patients diagnosed with AS to the total number of patients hospitalized in a specialized ENT department for emergency indications was 21.2%: fluctuations ranged from 13.5% to 30.7% depending on the season. From 2021 to 2022, 500 children applied to the ENT room of the admission department of the hospital, of which 5.7% were diagnosed with AS.

120 children with acute ENT pathology were hospitalized in a specialized ENT department, 21.2% of which were diagnosed with AS. Among all patients diagnosed with AS (n=54), boys predominated 53.4% (n=29). Most often, patients had signs of sinusitis - in 93.7% of cases, a little less often - ethmoiditis - in 32.8%. In third place in terms of frequency of occurrence is

frontal sinusitis - 21.7%. It is extremely rare that the sphenoid sinus is affected (0.7%), which is primarily due to the difficulty in diagnosing sphenoiditis. Complicated course of AS was noted in 8.3% (n=5) of cases.

Thus, acute sinusitis accounts for 5.7% of all diseases of the upper respiratory tract (fluctuations depending on the time of year from 2.5% to 8.2%) among children applying to the emergency department of the hospital and 21.2% (fluctuations depending on the time of year), from the time of year (from 13.5% to 30.7%) among patients of the specialized ENT department.

References:

1. Nurov U. I., Ikramova F. S., Alimova S. A. Immunological Aspects of Chronic and Recurrent Acute Rhinosinusitis in Children //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 31-35.
2. Нурова Г.У., Нуров У.И., Сулейманов С.Ф. СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ ВАЗОМОТОРНЫМ РИНИТОМ. Тиббиётда янги кун. 2019 –№ 2 (22) – С.149-151.
3. Firangiz Suleymanovna Ikramova. "TACTICS OF TREATING ALLERGIC RHINITIS WITH CHRONIC DIFFUSE DISEASES OF THE LIVER" Scientific progress, vol. 2, no. 7, 2021, pp. 1247-1252.
4. Х. Н. Нуриддинов ЭНДОСКОПИЧЕСКАЯ КАРТИНА ПРИ ПОЛИПОЗНОМ РИНОСИНУСИТЕ // Scientific progress. 2022. №4.
5. Firangiz Suleymanovna Ikramova. "TACTICS OF TREATING ALLERGIC RHINITIS WITH CHRONIC DIFFUSE DISEASES OF THE LIVER" Scientific progress, vol. 2, no. 7, 2021, pp. 1247-1252.